

1 Acoustic Monitoring of Oxygen Ebullition Reveals Hidden 2 Productivity in a Seemingly Heterotrophic Seagrass Meadow

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11 Abstract

12 Oxygen ebullition is typically ignored in long-term measurements of net ecosystem produc-
13 tivity (NEP), which reflects whether systems are net heterotrophic or autotrophic based on diel
14 changes in oxygen. The solubility of oxygen in seawater is a function of temperature, salin-
15 ity, and pressure. Warm, high-salinity seawater has low oxygen solubility, and when combined
16 with the photosynthetic productivity of macrophytes in shallow, clear waters, oxygen ebulli-
17 tion frequently occurs. The presence of mixed-phase oxygen in supersaturated seawater creates
18 difficulties for oxygen measurements because sensors cannot measure dissolved and gas phases
19 simultaneously. Therefore, dissolved oxygen measurements must be taken in conjunction with
20 separate ebullition measurements to develop an accurate oxygen budget needed to character-
21 ize NEP. Here, we seek to understand the drivers of NEP for a *Thalassia testudinum* meadow
22 in the Gulf of Mexico and calculate ebullition rates using acoustic sensing. We hypothesize
23 that oxygen ebullition will significantly increase NEP, particularly during the summer months
24 because of photosynthetic dependence on temperature and irradiance. We found the seagrass
25 meadow is typically oxygen saturated during the hours 07:00–22:00 with maximum saturation
26 occurring at 14:00. Acoustic-based methods and general additive modeling both found highest
27 ebullition rates in July/August. High respiration and air-sea exchange led to an apparent net
28 heterotrophic system ($NEP = -263 \text{ mg O}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$), but accounting for ebullition causes the
29 system to be autotrophic ($NEP = 71 \text{ mg O}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$). This study demonstrates the impor-
30 tance of including ebullition into NEP calculations and the viability of acoustics as a tool for
31 monitoring aquatic productivity.

1 Introduction

Photosynthetic fixation of carbon fuels the metabolism of nearly half a million plant and algae species, producing 17.75 Gt O₂ y⁻¹ as a byproduct that sustains aerobic life [1]. Anthropogenic activities (e.g., fossil-fuel combustion, large-scale cattle farming) are leading to an apparent global deoxygenation of the atmosphere and oceans [1, 2]. Careful, small-scale tracking of oxygen is needed to fully understand the drivers of global declines. At the ecosystem level, the balance between gross primary production (GPP) and respiration (R) is known as net ecosystem productivity (NEP, NEP = GPP - R). GPP and R are antagonistic processes, where GPP represents photosynthetic production of oxygen and R is the active consumption of oxygen to fuel biological metabolism [3]. If GPP > R (NEP > 0), more carbon is fixed in photosynthesis than lost during respiration, allowing the ecosystem to act as a long-term carbon sink. Conversely, ecosystems with GPP < R (NEP < 0) signify that the ecosystem is an active source of carbon to the atmosphere and other ecosystems. Global estimates have revealed that estuaries, lakes, ponds, and streams [4] act as sinks because of low productivity or high biological activity whereas seagrass meadows [5] and the surface ocean [6] are sources that have greater productivity and/or lower respiration (Table 1). NEP varies dynamically with the physiological state of the ecosystem, and thus exhibits large spatiotemporal variability with seasons, time of day, and community composition [3, 7]. Therefore, accurate measurements of oxygen are needed to construct the detailed budgets used to assess ecosystem health and productivity.

Table 1: Global average aquatic ecosystem production values (mg O₂ m⁻² d⁻¹).

Ecosystem	GPP	R	NEP	Source
Estuary	337.5	425	-87.3	[4]
Pond/Wetland	103.1	181.3	-78.1	[4]
Lake	181.3	190.6	-9.4	[4]
Stream	75	209.4	-131.3	[4]
Seagrass Meadow	224.9	187.6	27.2	[8]
Surface Ocean	206.3	81.3	90.6	[6]

The spatiotemporal variability of atmospheric oxygen is relatively low (e.g., 19.98 to 20.946% composition) compared with the intense diel cycles common in aquatic environments (<30 to >100% saturation) because of oxygen's greater abundance in the atmosphere and the relatively low solubility of oxygen in water [5, 9, 10]. Furthermore, physical processes (e.g., wave action, bubble injection, freezing) may further increase the oxygen concentration of water by introducing atmospheric gasses [11, 12]. The ability of gasses (i.e., O₂) to dissolve and saturate water is primarily a function of temperature, salinity, and pressure. Oxygen saturation is lowest in warm, shallow, salty ecosystems [13]. Consequently, regions with such characteristics and high primary productivity promote oxygen supersaturation and ebullition (spontaneous gas bubble formation). Currently, ebullition research is biased towards freshwater systems and/or greenhouse gasses (e.g., CH₄, CO₂, N₂O) despite the high degree of O₂ saturation (over 300%) in some coastal marine ecosystems [5, 13–15]. Freshwater ecosystems can have significant fluxes of oxygen through ebullition; measurements from a pond revealed that ebullition transports 21% of the oxygen produced in the system (i.e., NEP) to the atmosphere [16] and ebullitive fluxes rival diffuse atmospheric fluxes in some lakes [17]. Similarly,

64 up to 20% of the productivity in coral reefs may be lost as bubbles that are common sources of
65 sound in the ambient reef soundscape [18, 19]. Some seagrass meadows may lose up to 100% of their
66 productivity, severely underestimating NEP [20]. Therefore, it appears to be critical to include O₂
67 ebullition into NEP studies (especially in shallow, long residence time photosynthetic systems), but
68 very few have done so, and none over a long-time scale.

69 Mixed-phase oxygen in supersaturated seawater precludes simple measurement. Currently, there
70 are three main methods for measuring oxygen concentrations: iodometric, electrochemical, and
71 optical [21]. Iodometric titrations, also known as Winker titrations, are used as an international
72 benchmark because of their high accuracy and precision, but they do not allow for continuous field
73 sampling or gaseous oxygen samples [22]. Both optical and electrochemical sensors are accurate
74 and can be designed to measure oxygen in either gas or dissolve phases, but not simultaneously
75 [23, 24]. Consequently, multiple sensors and a bubble trap would be needed to measure dissolved
76 and ebullitive oxygen fluxes in-situ. Modern solid-state sensors are resistant to degradation, require
77 little maintenance compared to other technologies, and quickly respond to fluctuating environmental
78 conditions, making them perfect for use in dynamic coastal environments, but also need multiple
79 sensors for gaseous and dissolved oxygen measurements [21]. Sound propagation is sensitive to the
80 presence of bubbles, which cause the attenuation, scattering, and dispersion of sound. Acoustic
81 methods have been used to assess changes in oxygen production of seagrass meadows with high
82 temporal resolution [25–29]. Therefore, acoustic remote sensing methods offer an opportunity to
83 develop an accurate oxygen budget to characterize net ecosystem productivity in seagrass meadows
84 by making gas phase measurements in conjunction with dissolved oxygen measurements.

85 Seagrasses are highly productive marine plants distributed globally across temperate and tropical
86 climates [30]. Meadows provide numerous ecosystem services including carbon sequestration, sed-
87 iment stabilization, animal food/habitat, and nutrient cycling [31]. Global seagrass areal coverage
88 and diversity are declining due to a variety of factors including disease, eutrophication, habitat loss,
89 heat waves, storms, and sea level rise [32–34]. Recently, there is considerable interest in the capabil-
90 ities of seagrass meadows as carbon sinks, given their high NEP [8, 35]. Typically, NEP is highest
91 during the late summer/early fall in temperate and subtropical regions because of optimal light and
92 temperature [36]. However, some NEP measurements suggest that not all seagrass meadows are sinks
93 and might be sources of carbon [3, 8, 37]. Furthermore, other processes such as calcification may
94 further complicate the budget, highlighting the need for accurate NEP measurements [37]. Given
95 O₂ ebullition represents a large proportion of productivity of *Zostera marina* meadows in Virginia
96 [20], we predict that it also be important in other seagrass systems. Here, we seek to understand
97 the importance of O₂ ebullition to NEP across multiple years for a *Thalassia testudinum* dominated
98 meadow in the western Gulf of Mexico. We employed a novel acoustic observation system to esti-
99 mate the volume of gas bubbles present in the water column, paired with dissolved oxygen sensors.
100 We hypothesize that including oxygen ebullition will significantly increase estimates of ecosystem
101 productivity, particularly during the summer months because of photosynthetic dependence on tem-
102 perature and irradiance and optimal oxygen saturation conditions.

103 2 Materials and Methods

104 2.1 Study Design

105 East Flats is a popular fishing spot in Corpus Christi Bay, TX because of its abundant seagrasses
106 (Figure 1). The shallow water (<1.5 m) and stable environment permit *Thalassia*, a climax seagrass
107 species, to dominate the region [38]. *Halodule wrightii* and *Syringodium filiforme* are also found in
108 patches or intermixed with *Halophila engelmannii* in the understory. Natural sand patches prevent
109 the colonization of seagrasses in some areas, while anthropogenic fishing pressure causes occasional
110 prop-scars (no new prop-scars formed in the area during measurements). Our study took place from
111 25 October 2021 to 17 November 2023. Data was divided into hourly and monthly components to
112 understand scales of temporal variability. Overall, our objective was to understand the contribution
113 of ebullition to NEP over a two-year timescale. We collected ebullition measurements for one to
114 twenty-hour periods on fifteen occasions during the study period (Table S1, Figure S1).

Figure 1: Our study site, East Flats, is located within Corpus Christi Bay along the Texas Coast of the Western Gulf of Mexico. Green shading on the inset represents known seagrass coverage within the region [39] and the black circle is our study site. The drone photography shows the near-continuous seagrass meadow where measurements took place.

115 **2.2 Environmental Data**

116 Dissolved oxygen (DO) and temperature measurements were taken using either a miniDOT (PME,
117 California) or HOBO U26-001 (Onset, Massachusetts) logger with a 10-min sample period. Addition-
118 ally, water depth measurements were taken using a HOBO Pressure Logger (Onset, Massachusetts)
119 at a 10-min sample period. Sensors were placed in protective housings and cleaned every 2–3 months
120 to reduce biofouling.

121 The Mustang Beach Airport, located 3 km southeast of East Flats, collects meteorological mea-
122 surements every 20 minutes. We downloaded data spanning our deployment period including air
123 temperature, relative humidity, wind direction, air pressure, and wind speed from WeatherUnder-
124 ground (wunderground.com). We obtained irradiance data (measured as photosynthetically active
125 radiation) from the nearby Copano East station (<http://www.nerrsdata.org>) and supplemented gaps
126 using measurements from an hourly-integrated terrestrial PAR sensor at East Flats (LICOR, Ne-
127 braska).

128 **2.3 Biomass Cores**

129 Biomass cores were collected monthly starting in 2022. The cores were taken using a PVC corer (15
130 cm diameter) pushed ~25 cm into the sediment. Care was taken to avoid partially cutting leaves,
131 and only shoots inside the corer were included. Plant material was sieved, separated into above-
132 and below-ground portions, and dried to a constant mass.

133 **2.4 Ebullition Measurements**

134 **2.4.1 Ground Truth and Training Data**

135 We employed two different types of “traps” to catch ebullition evolving from seagrass meadows as
136 ground-truth data. First, we constructed manual bubble traps by replacing the sides of a traffic cone
137 (26 cm diameter) with clear vinyl sheeting, leaving only thin strips to retain the shape of the traffic
138 cone. We fastened a funnel threaded to fit 15 mL centrifuge tubes at the top of the cone to collect
139 the gas, which was held in the water column by buoyant floats. During deployments, tubes were
140 changed hourly, capped underwater, wrapped with parafilm, stored upside down to trap the bubble,
141 and transported on ice to the laboratory where they were stored at -80 °C. Vials were thawed
142 and allowed to re-equilibrate to collection temperature before the oxygen content was determined
143 using a Pyroscience OXF50-UHS sensor. Initial testing did not determine differences in fresh vs.
144 reconstituted ebullition, and the values fell within the expected values from the literature [17, 20,
145 40].

146 Second, we constructed automatic traps following the design of Juska [41, 42]. These traps contain
147 two HOBO U20L-04 pressure loggers (Onset, Massachusetts), pressure logger housing, gas collection
148 chamber, funnel, and PVC mount. One of the pressure loggers was sealed into the pressure logger
149 housing and connected to the gas collection chamber, and the second pressure logger measured the
150 ambient pressure. The amount of gas within the collection chamber was calculated from the change

151 in pressure between the two loggers. The openings of the funnels were positioned approximately 5
152 cm above the seafloor so that the seagrass leaves were constrained within the funnel[42].

153 Cones were placed within 10 m of each other ($n = 2-3$ per deployment, Table S1) at the end of
154 the acoustic array (described below). Sites were systematically chosen to contain 100% coverage of
155 the homogeneous seagrass meadow (primarily *Thalassia* and *Syringodium*). Any drift macroalgae
156 or dead seagrass were removed prior to placement of cones. Epiphytic and benthic microalgae were
157 left intact because they are part of the holistic seagrass meadow community and may contribute a
158 small portion of ebullition.

159 2.5 Acoustics

160 The acoustic system is described in greater detail by Ballard et al. [42]. Briefly, an exponential
161 frequency modulated chirp with a bandwidth of 0.5–100 kHz and a duration of 50 ms was broadcast
162 from a piezoelectric, omnidirectional acoustic source (M18C-4.0, GeoSpectrum Technologies) to
163 four hydrophones (HTI-94, High Tech Inc) located 1.5, 3, 6, and 12 m away. The source and all
164 four hydrophones were anchored to the bottom, with the sensing transducers located within the
165 seagrass canopy. The signal generation and data acquisition were operated autonomously with
166 a user programmable system (OceanEcho, JASCO Applied Sciences). Acoustic signals ($n = 5$)
167 were transmitted at one-second intervals every 10 min. The received signal from each hydrophone
168 was convolved with an inverse filter to obtain a band-limited impulse response, which contains the
169 waveguide impulse response, the responses of the source and the receiver, and any additive ambient
170 noise that is present [27]. The total received acoustic energy level at each hydrophone was computed
171 by integrating the square of the impulse response over the entire signal and then converting to a
172 decibel quantity [43]. Transmission loss (TL), a decibel quantity, was calculated by subtracting the
173 received acoustic energy level of the propagated signal from the total received acoustical energy level
174 of the source signal in the free-field normalized to 1 m[42]. In the following analysis, the broadband
175 TL of signals recorded on the hydrophone 1.5 m from the source is considered.

176 Ebullition is strongly correlated with both acoustic transmission loss (TL) and ambient sound
177 measurements [42]. TL data are influenced by both the aboveground biomass and free bubbles,
178 so the nighttime TL was subtracted from the total TL to obtain an estimate of the portion of
179 TL attributed to photosynthetic bubble production. Here, we use a previously described empirical
180 regression to estimate ebullition [42] from the same study:

$$E_{\text{TL}}(t) = -4.67 + \text{TL}_{\text{Bubbles}}(t) \times 10.12, \quad (1)$$

181 where $E_{\text{TL}}(t)$ is the ebullition determined from the portion of TL attributed to photosynthetic
182 bubble production $\text{TL}_{\text{Bubbles}}(t)$. Broadband TL (1 to 50 kHz) was used to create the regression,
183 since almost the entire frequency band was affected by photosynthetic bubble production [42]. Using
184 this regression, the acoustic data provide an estimate of gas flux, and the generalized additive model
185 (see below) provides the estimate of oxygen content.

2.6 Statistical Analysis

General additive models (GAMs) were constructed to evaluate the statistical relationship between ebullition flux/bubble oxygen content and environmental conditions because of the non-linear nature of the parameters [44]. The model basis functions were adjusted from their default values until smoothing was adequate, marked by either 1) visual inspection or 2) non-significant p -values and stable effective degrees of freedom. Various model families were tested, but assessment of model diagnostics led us to use the Gaussian distribution for both models. All environmental data were interpolated to 1-min period to match to the sample rate of the automatic ebullition traps and align in sampling times using the ImputeTS R package. Only automatic bubble trap data (gas flux ≥ 0) were used to create GAMs, ensuring direct comparability between the GAM and acoustic model [42]. Additionally, the independent manual bubble trap data from various points throughout the year was used to assess the fit of both models. Initial testing did not reveal significant differences in model outcomes based on interpolation. Gross primary production, respiration, and net ecosystem production were calculated with the available environmental data using an ordinal least squares method [45]. By definition, $GPP \geq 0$ & $R \leq 0$, but high air-sea exchange rates can cause calculated $GPP < 0$ & $R > 0$ as a numerical side effect [45, 46]. There is no current consensus on the best approach to handle cases where these non-physical values are present, whether by correction, filtering, or keeping values [45, 46]. Consequently, the numerically defined negative GPP removes NEP and positive R contributes towards NEP, although they lack physical analogs. We removed dates containing wind speeds ≥ 15.5 m s⁻¹ to limit confounding from wave-driven bubble injection. We tested multiple methods to account for air-sea exchange and adjust production values (Figure S2). Ultimately, we chose the method described by Nightingale [47] to represent an intermediate air-sea exchange scenario. We used the environmental data to calculate the Schmidt number for O₂ and K₆₀₀. The GAMs predict both the gas volume flux and the oxygen content of the gas.

3 Results

3.1 Environmental Context

Air/water temperatures and irradiance show both typical diel and seasonal patterns, with mid-day/summer highs and nighttime/winter lows (Figure 2A). Overall, water temperatures were warmer and less variable ($\bar{x} = 24.2$ °C, $\sigma = 6.2$) than air ($\bar{x} = 22.68$ °C, $\sigma = 6.7$). Water depth is controlled by a mixed semidiurnal secular tide with an average daily tidal range of 0.25 m ($\sigma = 0.09$), but maximum depths differ by up to 0.75 m across seasons (Figure 2B). Maximum midday irradiance values range from 1000 to 1500 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ from between winter and summer (Figure 2C). Warm southerly winds in the summer are replaced by stronger, colder frontal systems in the fall and winter (Figure S3). Consequently, seagrass biomass reaches a minimum during the early winter/spring and a maximum in late summer/early fall (Figure 2D) in response to these environmental conditions.

Figure 2: Local environmental conditions during net ecosystem productivity measurements show typical diurnal and seasonal patterns. A) Water and air temperature are highly correlated, B) water depth varies according to seasonal secular tides, C) irradiance (measured as PAR, $\mu E = \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) has summer maximum and winter minima, and D) seagrass biomass is greatest in late summer/early fall. Lines show LOESS (locally estimated scatterplot smoothing) lines with shading representing standard error.

222 3.2 Occurrence and Timing of Oxygen Supersaturation

223 Dissolved oxygen concentrations ranged from hypoxic to hyperoxic ($0.01\text{--}30.60\text{ mg L}^{-1}$) with nor-
224 moxic mean conditions ($\bar{x} = 7.38$, $\sigma = 3.56$; Figure 3A). Furthermore, concentrations were highest
225 at 14:00 ($\bar{x} = 11.42$, $\sigma = 3.19$; Figure 4A) and lowest early in the morning (5:00, $\bar{x} = 4.51$, $\sigma = 2.66$;
226 Figure 4A). Oxygen saturation mimicked these trends (Figures 3B). Seasonally, June had the lowest
227 average oxygen concentration ($\bar{x} = 5.75$, $\sigma = 3.75$) and saturation ($\bar{x} = 83.66$, $\sigma = 55.80$), while
228 February had the highest concentration ($\bar{x} = 10.65$, $\sigma = 2.22$) and September the highest saturation
229 ($\bar{x} = 110.11$, $\sigma = 75.31$). Waters typically did not reach 100% saturation until 07:00, reached a
230 maximum saturation amount by 14:00, and continued to stay saturated until 22:00 (Figure 4A).
231 Maximum saturation occurs in August to September (300–400%) while lowest occurs in December
232 and January (150%; Figure 4B).

Figure 3: Time series of dissolved oxygen concentration (A) and saturation (B) during net ecosystem metabolism measurements. Oxygen ebullition was enhanced or depressed at 100% O_2 saturation, indicated by the dashed line.

233 3.3 Predictions of Oxygen Ebullition

234 The interactive effects of light (measured as photosynthetically active radiation) and dissolved oxygen
235 saturation was a significant predictor ($p < 10^{-16}$) of ebullition rate ($\text{ml}_{\text{gas}}\text{ m}^{-2}\text{ h}^{-1}$) from the seagrass
236 meadow during our study ($R^2 = 0.96$, Deviance Explained = 96.2%). Generally, ebullition increases
237 with increasing DO saturation, but ebullition is enhanced between 0 and $750\ \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2}$
238 s^{-1} (Figure 5A). Furthermore, the interactive effects of photosynthetically active radiation and
239 atmospheric pressure are a significant predictor ($p = 0.0233$) of the oxygen content of ebullition
240 ($R^2 = 0.244$, Deviance Explained = 33.2%). The oxygen content of bubbles increases during low
241 pressure systems and is slightly modified by light (Figure 5B). Our training dataset of ebullition
242 oxygen concentration was fairly constant throughout the day, but was lowest in early morning or

Figure 4: Dissolved oxygen (DO) saturation across diurnal and seasonal cycles. Boxplots represent the distribution of collected data during NEP monitoring, with individual points falling outside the 95% confidence interval. A) DO reaches maximum saturation at 14:00 and stays saturated for a large proportion of the day. B) August has the highest DO saturation.

243 late afternoon (Figure S4). Transmission loss (TL) was significantly correlated ($p < 10^{-16}$) with our
 244 automatic ebullition measurements (Figure 6; [42]).

245 Overall, GAM and acoustic estimates were highly correlated ($r = 0.72$, Figure S5). However, the
 246 fluxes from the acoustic model were less than those predicted from the GAM. Both models describe
 247 the shape and approximate magnitude of fluxes with hourly sample resolution (e.g., 8/30/2022,
 248 1/17/2023, and 3/23/2023), but often overpredict fluxes in the late afternoon (Figure S1). Like-
 249 wise, model results diverged compared to fluxes collected over multiple hours (e.g., 12/8/2021 and
 250 12/16/2021). Generally, the acoustic model fits novel ground truth data (i.e., manual bubble traps)
 251 with a lower root-mean-square error ($24.4 \text{ mg O}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$) and higher correlation ($r = 0.93$) than
 252 the GAM model ($41.0 \text{ mg O}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$, $r = 0.89$).

Figure 5: Partial effect plots from GAM modeling of A) gas ebullition rate from automatic bubble traps and B) O_2 content of gas bubbles from manual bubble traps. The black dashed lines indicate the standard error. Partial effects indicate the size and sign (brown > 0 , blue < 0) of the relationship between independent and dependent variables.

253 3.4 Net Ecosystem Production

254 Air-sea exchange has a significantly greater control on dissolved oxygen than photosynthetic pro-
 255 duction alone (compare Figures 7A-D & 8A-D). At the ecosystem level, gross primary productivity
 256 (GPP) and respiration (R) were highest in the summer and lowest in the winter (Figures 8A,B).
 257 Overall, the system's net productivity is relatively balanced throughout the year (Figures 8C,D).
 258 However, air-sea exchange is an important process (especially in shallow seagrass meadow where
 259 high wind can mask biological productivity) and cannot be ignored [48]. Corrected GPP and R
 260 have strong seasonal patterns, with high R and low GPP from April–August (Figures 7A,B). Conse-
 261 quently, this leads to the lowest mean net ecosystem productivity (NEP) in July ($-365 \text{ mg O}_2 \text{ m}^{-2}$
 262 d^{-1}). Corrected R values are lowest and GPP are highest from November to January, leading to the

Figure 6: Linear regression of ebullition and acoustic transmission loss (see [42] for more details). The blue line represents the linear regression model with standard error shading.

263 highest NEP (mean $-190 \text{ mg O}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ in December). Overall, without including contributions
 264 from ebullition, the system appears net heterotrophic (average NEP = $-270 \text{ mg O}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$; Fig-
 265 ures 7C,D). A strong seasonal pattern of high ebullition in the summer/fall and low ebullition in the
 266 spring/winter is visible in both the acoustic TL and GAM estimates of O_2 flux (Figure 7E,F). The
 267 GAM predicted larger fluxes than the acoustic model (max 1396 vs. $469 \text{ mg O}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$). However,
 268 both models estimate peak ebullition in June–August (maximum monthly average 812 vs. 300 mg
 269 $\text{O}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$; Figures 7E,F). Correcting NEP measurements by adding ebullition creates a seasonal
 270 pattern of lower productivity in the winter (average ebullition across both models + NEP = -25
 271 vs. NEP alone = $-221 \text{ mg O}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$) and high productivity in the summer (average ebullition
 272 across both models + NEP = 418 vs. NEP alone = $-334 \text{ mg O}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$; Figures 7G,H). Inclusion
 273 of ebullition using either median GAM and acoustic estimates increases NEP by 195% and 67%
 274 respectively. Furthermore, the system is net autotrophic with oxygen ebullition (average ebullition
 275 across both models + NEP = $88 \text{ mg O}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$).

276 4 Discussion

277 This study monitors seagrass net ecosystem productivity and uses acoustics to quantify the impor-
 278 tance of oxygen ebullition within Corpus Christi Bay. Over two years of our study, gross primary
 279 productivity and respiration cycles across seasons showed high NEP in summer and low NEP in
 280 winter that follows typical seasonal cycles in seagrass biomass. Accounting for air-sea exchange
 281 reverses this relationship because strong winds mask biological productivity in shallow ecosystems,
 282 but estimates are in-line with values from similar estuaries. We found high rates of oxygen ebullition

Figure 7: Seagrass productivity budgets ($\text{mg O}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$) for East Flats with air-sea correction. Colors represent the same parameter. A, C, E, and G show gross primary productivity & respiration, net ecosystem productivity, acoustic and GAM estimates of ebullition, and NEP + ebullition, respectively. B, D, F, H are monthly boxplots representing the distribution of collected data with individual points falling outside the 95% CI. 13

Figure 8: Seagrass productivity budgets for East Flats without air-sea correction. All graphs and the same parameter(s) within a row. A & C show gross primary productivity & respiration and net ecosystem productivity respectively. B & D are monthly boxplots representing the distribution of collected data, with individual points falling outside the 95% CI.

283 in the summer, supporting observations of oxygen ebullition in diverse ecosystems worldwide. Year-
284 round ebullition turns the meadow from net heterotrophic to net autotrophic, adding to the growing
285 body of evidence that oxygen ebullition should be added to NEP measurements. Statistical mod-
286 eling revealed that ebullition rates were significantly correlated to irradiance and dissolved oxygen
287 saturation, and the oxygen concentration of ebullition was controlled by atmospheric pressure and
288 irradiance. Acoustic estimates of ebullition were highly correlated to those from general additive
289 models, highlighting the relevance of acoustic sensing to traditional biological methods.

290 4.1 Study Limitations

291 Open-water methods have been commonly used for estimating NEP for decades, but there are un-
292 certainties in sampling area and they cannot easily distinguish between benthic (seagrasses) and
293 water column (phytoplankton) fluxes [49, 50]. Newer techniques (e.g., aquatic eddy covariance)
294 can overcome these limitations, but are costly and technologically challenging to implement [51].
295 However, most NEP in nearby Laguna Madre comes from seagrasses, not phytoplankton [50] and
296 East Flats is shallow and has low water column chlorophyll *a* [38], so we expect open-water NEP
297 measurements to represent mostly benthic fluxes. Likewise, we expect most ebullition to originate
298 from seagrasses, since we noted little algal fouling by epiphytes and drift algae during the exper-
299 iment. However, other unaccounted processes may affect NEP such as oxygen consumption by
300 chemoautotrophs (e.g., nitrification), oxidation of reduced chemical species (e.g., metals), or chem-
301 ical processes (e.g., calcification, carbonate formation) [37, 52]. Furthermore, air-sea exchange is
302 difficult to quantify at the site level without passive gas tracers, so our approximations using at-
303 mospheric measurements from the nearby airport may not exactly represent the in-situ conditions
304 [48]. Our data collected from the automatic bubble trap is a relatively small “training” dataset for
305 our GAM and acoustic model that can be improved for future studies by improving replication and
306 reducing potential leakage [42]. However, we found model fluxes generally agreed with the shape and
307 magnitude of several independent manual bubble trap deployments (Figure S1). We hypothesize
308 that the gas flux captured by overnight bubble traps happened closer to deployment than recovery,
309 which would bias gas flux values. Likewise, we saw multiple depressions in measured gas flux, but
310 not predicted gas flux. This suggests that another factor beyond light and temperature were affect-
311 ing fluxes or issues with the trap measurements. We hypothesize time points where the GAM and
312 acoustic model agree, but not with the bubble trap (e.g., 17:30 on 8/30/2022) are due to issues with
313 the bubble trap. We found irradiance and dissolved oxygen saturation were highly correlated with
314 gas flux rates, but future testing should include more measurements to better capture seasonal and
315 environmental differences. Finally, bubble traps may introduce “chamber effects” by altering the
316 physical environment, but we felt floating traps would risk losing ebullition and introduce lateral
317 flux.

318 4.2 Net Ecosystem Production

319 We report air-sea corrected heterotrophic NEP values (-500 to 0 mg O₂ m⁻² d⁻¹) that are consistent
320 with values of many pristine estuaries of the Gulf of Mexico and southeastern USA [3]. However, our

321 NEP values are lower than previously reported for global seagrass meadows (normally autotrophic
322 or in-balance) [8, 49, 50]. NEP budgets often neglect air-sea exchange, which can be a significant
323 flux of gasses in coastal ecosystems and is often ignored in larger scale modeling [48, 53].

324 Many ecosystems show latitudinal gradients of increasing NEP from temperate zones towards
325 the tropics [54–57]. However, seagrass meadows appear to follow the opposite trend, despite clear
326 water and high biomass causing greater GPP in the tropics [8]. However, increased dissolved oxygen
327 production, driven by higher GPP [8], paired with the lowered saturation point of warmer waters [58]
328 may lead actually to a greater rate of ebullition in the tropics. Such increased oxygen ebullition may
329 shift the relationship between temperate and tropical ecosystems when accounted for in productivity
330 budgets. Future research should measure the impact of ebullition on NEP from a variety of seagrass
331 species and locations to determine its global impact.

332 4.3 Composition of Gas Bubbles

333 Macrophyte gas ebullition produces a relatively constant O₂ gas fraction between 20–40%, regardless
334 of lineage (Figure S4). Long et al. [20] found bubbles from *Zostera marina* contained between 20–
335 40% O₂ and Shikani et al. [40] found 21–45% for three species of aquarium plant regardless of lineage.
336 Indeed, we found that O₂ content in gas ebullition from a mixed *Thalassia testudinum* meadow
337 ranged from 17–43% (Figure S4). The remaining 83–57% gas composition of bubbles is unknown, but
338 preliminary sampling revealed elevated methane concentrations in some samples (data not shown).
339 Previous work has shown significant methane ebullition from seagrass meadows in the area [59].
340 Ebullition at the ecosystem level may have much lower O₂ content and contain high concentrations
341 of other gasses (e.g., N₂, CH₄, CO₂) reducing the effective carbon sink potential of these systems
342 [60–62]. Therefore, while gas ebullition represents a significant flux of O₂ that is ignored in NEP
343 measurements, these bubbles may also contain significant concentrations of greenhouse gasses that
344 compromise their ability to act as carbon sinks.

345 4.4 Importance of Oxygen Ebullition in NEP Measurements

346 Oxygen ebullition has long been recognized across various ecosystems, but its ecological importance
347 is undervalued. Koschorreck et al. compiled data on oxygen ebullition literature and found it reported
348 as early as the 1940s and present in both fresh- and saltwater ecosystems [17]. The biogeochemical
349 consequences of these bubbles have only recently been investigated with various studies finding them
350 to represent significant oxygen fluxes [16, 17, 19, 20]. When calculating regional oxygen budgets,
351 (e.g., NEP or deoxygenation) such oxygen fluxes have often been ignored and consequently lead to
352 inaccurate budgeting in coastal regions [16]. The potential for error propagation is large, given the
353 enormous area of coastal productivity [5]. Here, we found that incorporation of ebullition increased
354 productivity by 101–112%, consistent with other studies [19, 20], except demonstrated over a longer
355 timescale. Therefore, we recommend further investigation into the prevalence of oxygen ebullition
356 and inclusion if present when measuring O₂ in aquatic environments.

4.5 Acoustic Measurements of Gas Ebullition

Dissolved oxygen regularly reaches supersaturation in coastal environments [5] and reached over 400% during our study. Dissolved oxygen sensors are widely used in seagrass productivity studies, but fail to accurately account for freely rising and attached bubbles formed during spontaneous O₂ ebullition. Our GAM indicated ebullition enhancement above 160% O₂ saturation (Figure 5a) whereas previous work has shown that acoustics are sensitive enough to detect ebullition beginning at 100% saturation [25–27, 42, 43]. The differences likely result from the sensitivity of acoustic waves to bubbles because they absorb and scatter sound [63]. Therefore, acoustics estimates may be more accurate because they are directly affected by the physical gas bubbles, whereas the GAM reflects the environmental conditions promoting ebullition. We predict with additional training data the two models will converge. Nevertheless, both estimates are strongly correlated and predict ebullition represents a significant O₂ flux with similar seasonal cycles and magnitudes. The seagrass meadows at East Flats are oxygen saturated from 08:00–22:00, indicating that oxygen budgets may not be accurate for a majority of the day and productivity during times of peak photosynthetic activity is underestimated using only dissolved oxygen sensors. The use of acoustic techniques rather than bubble traps appear to be a viable approach for long-term monitoring because acoustic sensors are not prone to leakage/breakage from tides/waves [42] and they require little manual intervention (e.g., no emptying and monitoring of traps). Additionally, acoustics offer high temporal resolution, providing enhanced insight into potential causes of ebullition [42]. Here, we applied GAMs that predicted more ebullition than the acoustic model. This is likely because our GAMs relied on correlating ebullition to mechanistic factors that may have confounding effects (e.g., dissolved oxygen saturation, irradiance), whereas the acoustic measurements relied on transmission loss, a metric directly sensitive and correlating to ebullition. Short-term bubble collections were used to provide meaningful correlations from acoustic information into bubble flux estimates and identify the composition of collected environmental ebullition. Furthermore, seasonal changes in TL can also provide a nondestructive, long-term measurement of above ground biomass with high temporal resolution [42]. Compared to point measurements from cores, which are often spatially and temporally biased, the acoustic estimate is spatially averaged over the length of the acoustic propagation path and sampling is automated for collection at high repetition rate.

4.6 Application of Data

Empirical regression models are valuable tools to understand the environmental drivers of ebullition and NEP, but they are ecosystem specific and require updated parameters for changes in experimental conditions (e.g., water depth, sediment type, canopy height). This study corroborates recent findings that demonstrate the importance of ebullition to NEP and the use of acoustics for long term monitoring of marine macrophytes [16–18, 20, 26, 27, 42]. Our work also shows that remotely sensed estimates of net ecosystem production provided by acoustical techniques can greatly inform global oxygen budgets and inform carbon monitoring, modeling, and capture efforts.

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398 **Author Contributions**

399 M. Ballard, K. Lee, P. Wilson, and K. Dunton, and K. Capistrant-Fossa conceived the idea and
400 designed the experiments. All authors collected data and conducted the experiment. K. Capistrant-
401 Fossa, M. Ballard, and K. Lee analyzed the data. All authors contributed equally to the writing of
402 the manuscript.

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409 **Conflicts of Interest**

410 The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this article.

411 **Data Availability**

412 All data and code needed to reproduce the study is freely accessible online (DOI pending).

413 **Supplementary Materials**

Figure S1: Comparison of acoustic and GAM estimates of gas flux built using data from the automatic bubble traps (9/27/2023 - 9/28/2023) and independent manual bubble traps from East Flats over the sensor deployment period. Black dots = bubble traps, orange = GAM, blue = acoustic model, green = average of both models.

Figure S2: Modeled air-sea gas transfer velocities according to various authors. Gas transfer values are normalized to a Schmidt number of 600.

Figure S3: Wind conditions across seasons at the Mustang Beach Airport, 3 km away from the East Flats study site.

Figure S4: The percentage of oxygen from ebullition collected using manual bubble traps. The black line represents atmospheric oxygen.

Figure S5: Comparison of acoustic and GAM estimates of oxygen ebullition ($\text{mg O}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$) from East Flats over the sensor deployment period. The red line represents a 1:1 ratio.

Table S1: Bubble trap deployment schedule.

Start Date	Start Time	End Date	End Time
12/8/2021	9:10 AM	12/8/2021	3:30 PM
12/8/2021	3:30 PM	12/9/2021	9:35 AM
12/16/2021	5:35 PM	12/17/2021	9:14 AM
12/17/2021	9:14 AM	12/17/2021	4:00 PM
1/4/2022	3:15 PM	1/5/2022	9:24 AM
1/5/2022	9:24 AM	1/5/2022	4:00 PM
1/5/2022	4:00 PM	1/6/2022	10:30 AM
8/30/2022	10:30 AM	8/30/2022	5:30 PM
8/31/2022	9:15 AM	8/31/2022	6:30 PM
9/3/2022	9:45 AM	9/1/2022	6:45 PM
1/17/2023	9:00 AM	1/17/2023	3:00 PM
1/19/2023	9:00 AM	1/19/2023	3:00 PM
3/7/2023	12:00 PM	3/7/2023	3:00 PM
3/23/2023	11:30 AM	3/7/2023	3:30 PM
9/27/2023	12:25 PM	9/28/2023	8:44 AM

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